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Executive summary

This document summarises the activities undertaken, results achieved, and deviations from the original plan, where applicable, for D2.2 Chemical/electrochemical remediation within WP2: Soil Pollution in Mediterranean olive groves. A search of the literature revealed few studies which describe the best available techniques for soil remediation for agronomic soils. Furthermore, data about the efficacy and safety of chemical and electrochemical remediation of agricultural soils are limited, where the health and biodiversity of the soil after treatment must not be significantly altered. Herein, the removal efficiency of common organic pesticides, such as atrazine, oxyfluorfen, and glyphosate, via chemical oxidation with ozone and hydrogen peroxide, and copper removal by electrokinetic remediation, was analysed in spiked soils and olive grove soils. To shed light on the impact on soil health and biodiversity, nematode mortality (and abundance) and soil basal and induced based respiration rate were monitored during chemical and electrochemical bench-scale remediation of soils from the orchard ES-HD22. Nematodes represent all trophic levels in the soil and are dependent of other organisms for their multiplication, predation or being food for other soil organisms. Nematode changes in mortality and abundance reflects the intrinsic mortality effect, but also effects on the organisms they feed. Two groups have been analysed by their feeding habit (plant-parasitic and the rest of nematodes known as free-living). Soil respiration is a key proxy for soil biodiversity and is parameter directly related to soil health.

Chemical remediation was conducted with electrochemically generated ozone gas and hydrogen peroxide in 3D-printed reactors. Reactors were designed in our research group for long service life, robustness for field use, scalability, integrability, environmental friendliness, and continuous operation capacity. Hydrogen peroxide achieved high atrazine removals, exceeding 90% in spiked soils and 67% in the orchard agricultural soil (ESHD22), evidencing matrix dependent performance; ozone reduced atrazine by 68% in spiked soils and 45% in the same agricultural soil. Glyphosate removal in agricultural soil dropped to 25% with hydrogen peroxide, whereas it was approximately 44% in the ozonation, indicating a nonselective nature of ozonation across organic pollutants for ozone. Notably, contaminant distribution showed higher removals near oxidant addition points, highlighting diffusion limited transport and the need for oxidant delivery optimisation. Nematode activity was negatively affected by hydrogen peroxide dosing, whereas ozone gas had a minimal observed effect under the conditions tested. These differences are likely attributed to the dosing mode (liquid vs gas). Overall, both oxidants are feasible for degrading target organics, with ozonation preferred where preservation of soil fertility is a priority.

For copper (Cu), strong retention in orchard soils necessitated chelating agents to enhance mobilisation and removal, as EKR with water removed less than 1% of Cu. Nitric acid, citric acid, EDTA and EDDS were tested at different concentrations in several soil matrices (gravel, sand, clay, and real soil). However, Cu removal was only enhanced using EDTA and EDDS, with >32% (0.1 M EDTA) and >23% (0.1 M EDDS) after 360 h via electromigration/electrophoresis in real soils. Benchs scale EKR with the biodegradable EDDS demonstrated directional Cu transport toward the anode and decreased concentrations farther from that electrode. Nematode mortality and respiration showed a low to moderate, distance dependent impact on microbial activity that can be mitigated by electrode placement and operating window optimisation. This supports the feasibility of efficient Cu reduction with minimal impact on soil fertility when using biodegradable chelating agents and tuned EKR configurations.

1. The novelty of this study

Soil contamination poses a significant challenge today, as it directly affects both health and food sources. It is well established that contamination can spread through diffusion into the air or groundwater, making it crucial to remove contaminants from the soil. Despite the importance of soil remediation, best available techniques (BAT) by the European Bureau of Research on Industrial transformation and Emissions do not provide specific guidelines, but rather contaminated soil is included in general waste treatment (https://bureau-industrial-transformation.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2019-11/JRC113018_WT_Bref.pdf). This document includes conventional techniques such as thermal desorption, soil washing, vapour extraction, solvent extraction, and biodegradation, but as it is clearly state BAT conclusions do not address to in situ remediation of contaminated soil. Similarly, the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) does not completely address this issue yet (<https://doi.org/10.4060/cb4894en>). It is important to mention that they are working on a guideline for the Best Management and Remediation Techniques for Polluted Soil, but its content is still unknown.

There are several common approaches for soil restoration, such as biological, physicochemical, and thermal treatments. From them, electrokinetic and oxidation techniques, included in the in-situ physicochemical treatment, have been considered effective for rapid and low-cost rehabilitation of soil. However, studies on real-contaminated agricultural soil are still scarce, as detailed below.

1.1 Electrokinetic remediation

The use of electrokinetic (EK) technologies to remediate soil has been explored during the last couple of decades due to their efficiency, versatility, and in-situ operation[3–5]. In brief, direct current is applied to the soil via electrodes to enhance the mobilisation of contaminants, such as heavy metals, through electroosmosis, electrophoresis, and electromigration[6]. However, there is limited evidence regarding the remediation of agricultural soils, where the post-treatment soil quality and health must be carefully assessed. For instance, a comparative inspection of the number of documents about electrokinetic studies, available in the SCOPUS database, is presented in Figure 1. Despite having over 1304 documents about general electrokinetic matter, the number drops significantly when other keywords are added, such as heavy metal, copper, soil, and agricultural soil. In the area related to WP2, only 7 documents regarding electrokinetic techniques in agricultural soil with copper have been found, which highlights the lack of investigation in this area and the necessity to expand the scope of research, particularly due to the vast difference in soil properties and the type of contamination.

Figure 1. Comparison of documents related to electrokinetic remediation.

Data from several studies have established that electrokinetic (EK) treatments remove heavy metals, including cadmium, mercury, and copper, from soil[7–10]. Interestingly, the efficiency of the remediation is strongly affected by the pollutant adsorption onto the soil particles, which depends on the way the pollutants are introduced into soils and their interaction with the soil matrix[11]. Some studies have shown that the application of electric fields is not enough to mobilise Cu ions. For example, little Cu mobilisation has been identified in copper sulphate-spiked kaolinite soil, diminishing the removal efficiency of the process since the transport of Cu ions to the electrode wells by electromigration or electrophoresis was limited[12]. To solve this problem, the addition of chemicals to the anolyte or catholyte has been proposed to increase Cu removal efficiencies in EKR. Namely, the use of ammonium acetate solutions (0.1 M) as the anolyte enhanced Cu removal efficiency, from 29.3 to 63.9%, in copper nitrate-spiked industrial soil[13,14]. However, this acetate can decompose upon exposure to temperature rise, releasing corrosive vapours with ammonia or acetic acid that can detrimentally affect soil biodiversity. Giannis et al have demonstrated that the effectiveness of EKR is also enhanced with the use of nitrilotriacetic acid, diethylenetriamine pentaacetate, and ethyleneglycol tetra acetic acid for Cu removal from spiked agricultural soil[15]. Removals in the range from 15 to 60% were achieved depending on the type and concentration of the chelate. Surprisingly, the chelate concentration is not directly associated with greater metal extraction efficiencies, likely associated with complex soil matrix interactions. Nevertheless, these chemicals present the same problems as ammonium acetate due to their potential negative effect on soil quality.

Since one of the challenges of remediating agricultural soils is maintaining their quality to be used after the operation of removal techniques, organic acids have been studied as chelating agents for such applications. Citric acid has been tested as the catholyte in the remediation of spiked farmland soil (CuSO_4), achieving a removal efficiency of 41%[16]. In another study by Figueroa et al., the addition of citric acid and

ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) in the electrolyte enhanced the mobility of Cu ions in the soil because of the formation of charged complexes[17]. Although this study was conducted with a real soil matrix, the contaminants were artificially introduced, which could reduce the adsorption to the soil particles, facilitating their removal. This problem has been investigated in mine tailings by comparing the removal of Cu in simulated (with CuSO₄) and actual contaminated soil[7]. Removals of up to 20.1% were obtained in simulated samples, but dropped to 13.4% in actual samples, corroborating the differences in the remediation of real soils. Therefore, it is key to study the influence of chelating agents on the Cu mobilisation in actual soils from Mediterranean olive orchards. Here, it is worth noting that actual contamination in agricultural soil is a consequence of continuous dosing of Cu-based fungicides for several years, leading to Cu accumulation, distribution, and retention, which is likely to be the case in olive grove soils. In addition, it has been demonstrated that the formulation of the fungicides plays a crucial role in the metal adsorption onto soil particles[18]. For instance, copper oxychloride fungicides can induce the formation of stable particle-like aggregates in porous media, increasing Cu retention, especially in alkaline environments where they can even interact with dissolved copper cations. This negative effect is suggested to be intensified at Cu²⁺ concentrations over 20 ppm.

Other authors suggest that the combination of EKR with reactive filter media (activated carbon and biochar) or sulfonic acid exchange resins (SER) can enhance Cu removal over 78% in spiked soils contaminated with copper sulphate and copper nitrate[12]. Although these approaches reduce the need for adding chemicals, their application in large-scale plants can be challenging due to the complexity and cost of implementing and operating such technologies.

Overall, it is evident that copper remediation of real-aged agricultural soils with EKR has not yet been fully explored in the literature since previous studies have focused on spiked soil contaminated with copper salts. The little evidence in real case studies has been conducted in industrial or mining soils. However, operation in agricultural soils is limited by the effect of the process on the health and biodiversity of the soil. Additionally, previous findings indicate that the efficiency of EKR is mainly determined by the characteristics of soil, including the presence of organic matter, pH, source of contamination, and Cu concentration. Hence, a deep analysis of the Cu removal from Mediterranean olive grove soils by EKR is key to understanding the feasibility of elevating the application of this technology to larger TRLs.

1.2 Chemical Oxidation

The chemical oxidation of organic pollutants is considered a straightforward approach to effectively remediate air, water, and soil[19–22]. In simple terms, pollutants are broken down after exposure to an oxidant, such as ozone or hydrogen peroxide, by direct or indirect addition/elimination chemical reactions[23,24]. This methodology has been used for over a century in the destruction of hazardous compounds in water and wastewater, but its application in soil is still under development. A quick search on the SCOPUS database (Figure 2) shows the strong interest in soil remediation by oxidation, totalling 3945 documents from 1995. Nevertheless, filtering the search for *soil remediation of pesticides with ozone or hydrogen peroxide* significantly reduced the number of documents to 142 and 26, respectively. However, it is important to note that these documents comprised the use of these oxidants with other techniques and the scope was mostly limited to spiked or industrial soils.

Figure 2. Comparison of documents related to chemical oxidation.

Ozone is a strong oxidant that not only decomposes organic pollutants on its own but can also indirectly break down pollutants with secondary oxidant species such as perhydroxyl, superoxide, ozonide, and hydroxyl radicals. These species are generated via the reactive decomposition of ozone on the surface of soil particles or in aqueous solutions[25]. It is important to note that the decomposition of ozone in the air ends up in oxygen molecules, leaving no traces of the oxidant, which is advantageous for environmental applications. In addition, previous research investigating the irrigation of ozonated water in soil for tomato growing has shown minor negative effects on the diversity and composition of soil microbial community, tomato production yield, fruit quality, and soil pH[26]. Even though the authors suggest that the treatment should be specifically tailored to specific crop conditions to avoid adverse effects, the main findings indicate the suitability of this technology for the degradation of organic pesticides in agricultural soils.

The treatment of soil with ozone gas has recently attracted attention for efficiently degrading organic pesticides. This approach avoids dissolving the gas in aqueous solutions, where ozone is more unstable and decomposes faster than in the gas phase. Previous studies demonstrated that ozonation can degrade over 60% of the pesticides Boscalid, Chlorantraniliprole, Flonicamid, Metribuzin, Triazole, Anilinopyrimidine, Strobilurin, and Neonicotinoid under lab and field conditions[27]. In both cases, the soil was synthetically contaminated to a concentration of 1 mg kg⁻¹ (of each pesticide) and exposed to ozone generated by the corona discharge method. Of interest here is the little influence of soil microbial activity in these experiments. A note of caution is due here since ozone can also degrade other organic components in soil, suggesting that individual analysis of its effect for each type of soil is required to diminish its influence on microbial activity.

There is also evidence on the effectiveness of combining ozonation with other techniques, such as solarisation, to remediate soils contaminated with amide pesticides[28]. Laboratory and greenhouse experiments showed that this combined treatment significantly enhanced pesticide degradation, particularly when ozone was applied at a depth of 10 cm. The results indicated that ozone can be combined effectively with other techniques to enhance the degradation of pesticides. A coupled oxidation system has also been suggested as an alternative approach to increase the degradation of organic pollutants. For example, an iron-activated ozone/persulfate (O₃/PS) oxidation system has been tested for remediating petroleum-contaminated soil[29]. Under optimal conditions, the system removed 46.8% of total petroleum hydrocarbons within 3 hours, highlighting the synergistic effects of multiple radicals, including sulphate radicals (SO₄·), hydroxyl radicals (OH·), and superoxide radicals (O₂·). However, there is a lack of evidence on the effect on soil quality and biodiversity, especially for large-scale applications in agricultural soils.

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is another well-known nonpersistent oxidant for the degradation of hazardous organic contaminants in soils[24]. Likewise, the mode of oxidation is carried out by a direct attack of the peroxide itself or an indirect attack of H₂O₂ intermediates such as hydroxyl radicals (·OH). Notably, most of the literature focuses on the Fenton process, which involves the use of ferrous iron to promote the formation of ·OH. For instance, the oxidative degradation of roxarsone in spiked paddy soils (15 mg kg⁻¹) has been studied with Fenton-derived hydroxyl radicals[30]. What is striking about this study is that roxarsone was successfully degraded with rainwater-borne hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) in concentrations of up to 121 µM, which highlights its strong oxidation capacity.

Studies on the application of hydrogen peroxide as a direct oxidant for the degradation of contaminants in soils are still limited[31]. One of the few studies in this area has been conducted in the treatment of chlorophenol-spiked soil with commercially available H₂O₂. Despite obtaining degradations over 80% of chlorophenols, the use of commercial H₂O₂ reduces its importance for in-situ applications, where operation costs, including storage facilities, maintenance, and transportation, have a significant impact.

As mentioned above, any potential technology aimed at the restoration of agricultural soils must consider the post-treatment soil conditions. A study by Wei et al. has investigated the impact of hydrogen peroxide on the bacterial diversity and enzyme activity during the remediation of glyphosate in synthetically contaminated soil[32]. Although H₂O₂ enhanced glyphosate degradation by 52%, the abundance of glyphosate-degrading bacteria, enzyme activity, and resistance gene expression was negatively affected. This study highlights the complex interactions between chemical and biological processes in agricultural soils that require specific investigation. Here, it should be emphasised that there is a lack of research on the effect of the oxidant on the biodiversity after soil remediation techniques.

Overall, it has been identified that ozone remediation in soil is mainly conducted by corona discharge, which requires high energy consumption, equipment maintenance, and auxiliary equipment to purify and dry oxygen. In the case of hydrogen peroxide, most of the work is conducted with commercially available oxidant, increasing operational costs. Additionally, those studies are conducted with spiked soils and are limited in agriculture, where the effect of oxidants on soil quality is quite important to maintain soil use efficiency. The study of chemical oxidation in Mediterranean olive grove soils with ozone and hydrogen peroxide generated in situ and on-demand using electrochemical reactors can aid in overcoming this lack in the state of the art, particularly in the effect on soil biodiversity. Furthermore, the success of this environmentally friendly and sustainable process to produce H₂O₂ and O₃ can expand the application of chemical oxidation to other contaminated areas without environmental repercussions.

2. Experimental

Task 2.2 (M1-M42) Chemical and electrochemical remediation (UCLM, partners involved: UJA and CSIC)

Following the milestones from Task 2.2, *chemical oxidation* and *electrokinetic remediation* were designed and studied in this section, which are presented in their respective subtasks. In addition, to meet the recommendations from the reviewers in the Month 18 report, a series of experiments to determine the quality of real soil biodiversity after electrochemical and chemical oxidation remediation is also included in this deliverable. To do this, the orchard ES-HD22 orchard was selected and sampled again in February (15 triplicate sampling points: 45 samples in total). The soil was prepared in pots and transported to the UCLM facilities. For each treatment type, four trials of different durations (2, 7, 15, and 30 days) were carried out in triplicate, in addition to a reference trial (also in triplicate) in which the soil was not treated and was simply kept at the same temperature and humidity conditions to assess natural nematode mortality. In total, 45 trials were additionally carried out at the UCLM facilities with the participation of researchers from the UJA (analysis of glyphosate/AMPA and soil respiration) and the CSIC (analysis of nematodes and soil diversity).

2.1. Subtask 1. Design and testing of electrochemical cells to generate H₂O₂.

The chemical oxidation of organic pesticides in soils from olive orchards requires the in situ and on-demand electrochemical generation of hydrogen peroxide. Since commercially available H₂O₂ is not ideal for this purpose, electrochemical cell prototypes were designed, following these conditions: long service life, robustness for use in farms, scalability, integrability, environmental friendliness (utilising green energy and minimising reagent use), and continuous operation capacity. To enhance oxidant production efficiencies, designs focused on optimising hydraulic and electrical connections, as well as efficient current distribution. The reactors were fabricated by 3D printing (additive manufacturing) with green and cost-effective materials.

Figure 3 shows the reactions involved in the electrochemical generation of H₂O₂ with PEM cells, which occur within the reactor under specific operational parameters including the current density (A/m²), type of electrode (carbon or metal gas diffusion electrode, GDE, etc.), and the type of electrolyte (sulphate or bicarbonate).

Figure 3. Hydrogen peroxide generation reaction.

Figure 4a illustrates the design of the Prototype 1 reactor for oxidant production that comprises several bipolar plates fabricated using 3D printing technology in the laboratory. The anode is a boron-doped diamond (BDD), and the cathode is a gas diffusion electrode (GDE) with an O₂ inlet. In the cathodic compartment, O₂ is reduced to H₂O₂ with the protons generated by water splitting in the anodic compartment. To facilitate the migration of protons from the anode to the cathode and close the circuit, a Nafion™ proton exchange membrane (PEM) was placed between the compartments. A simulation of the fluid dynamics (Figure 4b)

shows a homogeneous fluid velocity in the compartments, the absence of dead zones, and correct contact with the electrode surface, which indicates that the cell has optimal fluid-dynamic conditions.

Figure 4. Prototype 2 reactor for H₂O₂ production

Turning now to the operation of Prototype 2, Table 1 presents the batch production of H₂O₂ at current densities from 2.5 to 75.0 mA cm⁻², using 500 mM NaHCO₃ as the electrolyte at room temperature. The data indicate that the peroxide production increases with current density to a maximum of 540 mg l⁻¹ at 25 mA cm⁻². Further increases in the current density drop the production rate, likely due to the occurrence of competing secondary reactions at these currents.

Table 1. Hydrogen peroxide production at different current densities in batch operation

Current density (mA/cm ²)	H ₂ O ₂ production (mg/L)
2.5	340
5	450
10	460
25	540
50	520
75	460

Peroxide production in continuous mode using 500 mM NaHCO₃ as the electrolyte indicates that the production rate increases over time until reaching a plateau after 60 minutes of operation. Regarding the effect of the current density, it seems that current density proportionally promotes H₂O₂ production even at 50 mAcm⁻², which decreased the rate in the batch mode. For instance, H₂O₂ mass rates of 0.8, 2.3, 5.4, and 10.8 mg min⁻¹ were obtained at 5, 10, 25 and 50 mAcm⁻² at the equilibrium. Surprisingly, the faradaic efficiency of the electrokinetic process is comparable in the generation at 10, 25, and 50 mA/cm².

Table 2. H₂O₂ produced using different current densities and faradaic efficiency (NaHCO₃).

j (mA/cm ²)	5		10		25		50	
	[H ₂ O ₂] (mg/L)	Faradaic efficiency (%)						
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0.049	3.76	0.357	13.54	1.411	21.36	2.723	20.61
10	0.198	15.04	0.765	28.96	2.504	37.91	4.970	37.61
15	0.318	24.07	1.093	41.37	3.389	51.30	6.769	51.23
30	0.566	42.88	1.878	71.09	4.781	72.37	9.582	72.52
45	0.725	54.91	2.047	77.48	5.298	80.19	10.576	80.04
60	0.725	54.91	2.226	84.26	5.387	81.55	10.844	82.07
75	0.805	60.93	2.266	85.76	5.675	85.91	10.804	81.77
90	0.874	66.20	2.306	87.26	5.317	80.49	10.884	82.37
105	0.765	57.92	2.296	86.89	5.427	82.15	10.854	82.15
120	0.745	56.42	2.286	86.51	5.407	81.85	11.162	84.48
150	0.775	58.68	1.918	72.59	5.635	85.31	10.446	79.06

To understand the effect of the electrolyte, sodium percarbonate (500 mM) was also tested at the same operational conditions as the one with sodium bicarbonate (Table 3). However, peroxide production was less efficient compared to sodium bicarbonate. Additionally, it indicates that Faradaic efficiency (%) does not exhibit a consistent trend.

Table 3. Moles of oxidant produced and faradaic efficiency using different current densities with sodium percarbonate as the electrolyte.

j (mA/cm²)	5		10		25		50	
Time (min)	[oxidant] (mmol/min)	Faradaic efficiency (%)	[oxidant] (mmol/min)	Faradaic efficiency (%)	[oxidant] (mmol/min)	Faradaic efficiency (%)	[oxidant] (mmol/min)	Faradaic efficiency (%)
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0.027	70.09	0.032	41.25	0.061	31.68	0.027	7.11
10	0.021	56.30			0.034	17.74	0.059	15.22
15	0.028	74.47			0.023	11.83	0.071	18.28
30					0.136	70.41	0.034	8.89
45					0.154	79.67	0.112	29.01
60	0.042	108.74	0.085	109.59	0.083	43.18	0.066	17.12
75					0.128	65.90	0.175	45.03
90					0.067	34.55	0.084	21.85
105					0.027	14.13	0.114	29.46
120					0.006	3.36	0.061	15.91
150	0.044	113.32			0.044	22.76	0.099	25.55

Consequently, it is concluded that sodium bicarbonate is a more effective electrolyte than sodium percarbonate, and thus, sodium bicarbonate was selected as the optimum electrolyte for H₂O₂ production with our electrochemical cell.

2.2. Subtask 2. Design and testing of electrochemical cells to generate gaseous O₃.

Considering that the objective of this study is the generation on demand and in situ of the oxidants, the electrochemical generation of gaseous ozone from water oxidation was attempted. Figure 5 shows the electrochemical reactions involved in this process: Water splits at the anode, generating ozone (O₃) and protons, while at the cathode, these protons are reduced to molecular hydrogen. This method offers several advantages over the corona discharge method, including operation at low voltage, higher energy efficiency, production of high-purity ozone, increased durability, and the elimination of the need for pure oxygen storage, compressors, or air conditioning units. Additionally, it is simple to operate and control, facilitating its further implementation at the field scale.

Figure 5. Ozone generation reaction

To optimise the electrochemical generation of ozone, two novel electrochemical cells were designed based on the concept of a membrane electrode assembly (MEA) and manufactured using 3D printing technology. The prototype 1 (Figure 6a) is a single-compartment cell with lattice boron-doped diamond (BDD) electrodes, where the electrolyte inlet and outlet are placed on top of the cell. The anolyte and catholyte are recirculated in their respective chambers, which are separated by a Nafion™ PEM. However, this design led to the accumulation of bubbles inside the cell, diminishing the production of ozone. For this reason, a second cell (prototype 2 shown in Figure 6b) was designed, with the electrolyte inlet relocated to the side of the cell and the outlet reshaped to facilitate bubble expulsion, thereby improving its functionality.

Figure 6. Prototype 1 (a) and 2 (b) PEM ozone cell and installation design

Prototype 2 was tested with current intensities of 3A and 4A to determine its effect on ozone production. For both intensities, ozone generation increased over time during the first minutes of operation before reaching a plateau at around 0.02 mg min^{-1} . Interestingly, little difference in the ozone production was observed after the stabilisation. A note of caution is due here since increasing the intensity from 3 to 4 A might not be sufficient to induce notable changes.

2.3. Subtask 3. Chemical remediation of soil with H₂O₂ electrogenerated

Prior to applying H₂O₂ to the real soil, a preliminary soil washing test was conducted using the oxidant as the washing solution to determine its herbicide degradation efficiency. For this experiment, soil was artificially contaminated with oxyfluorfen and atrazine (the herbicides) in concentrations of 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2 mg kg⁻¹, mixed with an aqueous oxidant solution (1000 mg l⁻¹), and agitated (150 rpm) for 24 hours. The herbicides were extracted from the soil following the QuEChERS extraction method and measured by high-performance liquid chromatography – mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS). Figure 7 presents the removal percentage of the herbicides by soil washing. What stands out in the figure is the complete degradation of atrazine (ATZ) in the less contaminated soil (0.5 mgkg⁻¹), as this pesticide was not identified in the soil after washing. In contrast, only 27.5% of oxyfluorfen (OXY) was removed, indicating a superior degradation performance for ATZ. Surprisingly, increasing the herbicide concentration enhanced the removal of OXY but diminished ATZ removal. As a result, OXY and ATZ removals of 81 and 69%, respectively, were obtained at an herbicide concentration of 2 mgkg⁻¹, suggesting that the effectiveness for both pesticides is similar at larger concentrations.

Figure 7. Pesticide removals (%) from the artificially contaminated soil by washing with H₂O₂ solutions (1000 mg l⁻¹).

Having defined the oxidation capacity of H₂O₂ for ATZ and OXY degradation by washing, artificially contaminated soil in concentrations of 0.1 and 1.5 mg kg⁻¹ was treated in 3D-printed cylindrical mock-ups (Figure 8). H₂O₂ (34.2 ml, 1000 mg l⁻¹) was added into the soil from the top of the mock-up at a flow rate of 1.14 mL min⁻¹ for 30 mins. These conditions allowed the mobilisation of the solution from the top to the bottom, maximising the exposure of the soil to the oxidant. Since the concentration of peroxide may vary along the mock-up, three vertical sections were equally divided (section A: 0-5 cm, section B: 5-10 cm, and section C: 10-15 cm) to assess the residual pesticide concentration in the soil (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Mock-up used in the soil remediation with H₂O₂.

Table 4 presents the removals of OXY and ATZ in concentrations of 0.1 and 1.5 mg per kg of soil. As expected, ATZ removals of 100% were achieved at an herbicide concentration of 0.1 mgkg⁻¹ and decreased with concentrations of 1.5 mgkg⁻¹. Surprisingly, the removal of OXY was also higher at the lowest pesticide concentration, which is contrary to what was observed in the washing experiments. Another interesting aspect of the table is the considerable difference in pesticide removals along the vertical sections. For the soil contaminated with 0.1 mgkg⁻¹ of OXY, a complete removal (100%) was observed in the bottom section, but decreased to 40.5% in the top section. This might indicate that the degradation of OXY requires longer residence times, which can be achieved in the bottom of the mock-up due to liquid accumulation. On the other hand, ATZ degradation was higher in the top section, where removals of up to 96.8% were calculated at the same herbicide concentration. Since the concentration of H₂O₂ is likely to be higher in this section, it is possible that a rapid degradation occurs, decreasing the oxidant concentration that flows to the next sections. In general, the results of soil contaminated with 1.5 mg/kg of both pesticides show higher ATZ removals (ranging between 60-90%) compared to OXY, which was less than 20% across all three sections. This suggests that at higher herbicide concentrations, H₂O₂ (1000 mg l⁻¹) is insufficient for effective oxyfluorfen removal.

Table 4. Pesticide removals at different concentrations using H₂O₂ as oxidant.

Pesticide	Contamination (µg/kg)	Removal (%)		
		Section A	Section B	Section C
Oxyfluorfen	1500	13.34	4.38	8.875
	100	40.52	65.67	100
Atrazine	1500	96.87	73.91	56.73
	100	100	98.08	100

To study the influence of chemical oxidation on soil biodiversity, soil samples from several areas of the orchard ES-HD22 were collected in rectangular plant pots (17x17x25 cm³), as seen in Figure 9a. Each pot was used to evaluate the elimination of glyphosate, nematode mortality, and soil respirometry after daily additions of H₂O₂ aqueous solutions (50 ml) for 2, 7, 15, and 30 days in triplicate. The oxidant was produced on demand in a dual-compartment PEM cell. Blank experiments were also conducted using the same experimental conditions with pure water instead of hydrogen peroxide solutions. The H₂O₂ aqueous solutions were distributed on top of the soil with a syringe to enhance the exposure of the oxidative species to the pesticides while diffusing from the surface to the bottom horizons. A scheme of the process is presented in Figure 9b.

a)

b)

Figure 9. a) Pots used in the remediation of agricultural soils from olive orchards. b) Scheme of the H₂O₂ remediation of agricultural soils contaminated with organic pesticides.

The dose of the oxidant was carefully followed to estimate the ratio of eliminated GLY / added H₂O₂ (wt.) and analyse the performance of the PEM cell under continuous operation. The accumulated mass of H₂O₂ added into the soil over the duration of the experiment is presented in Figure 10. The minor differences from day to day are related to the concentration of the peroxide solutions generated in the electrochemical cell.

In general, H_2O_2 generation was stable during the whole experiment. Interestingly, higher oxidant concentrations were obtained at the end of the experiment, highlighting the robust cell design to operate for on-demand applications. Doses of 26.3, 107.9, 227.9, and 827.6 mg were applied after 2, 7, 15, and 30 days, representing an oxidant/contaminant ratio (wt.) of approximately 60, 250, 500, and 2000.

Figure 10. Accumulated mass of H_2O_2 that was poured onto the mock-ups during the treatment.

Of surprise here was the concentration of GLY before and after the oxidant remediation was negligible and below the detection limits, which was unexpected since soil from the orchard ES-HD22 showed concentrations as high as $102.17 \text{ ug kg}^{-1}$. This highlights the complexity of remediating real contaminated soils where the contaminant concentration is highly heterogeneous and can fluctuate across the orchard, where sites without contamination can be found. Therefore, it is possible that soil aliquots were taken from these low-concentration areas in the orchard. To complete the information about pesticide degradation, the same agricultural soil was artificially contaminated with GLY and ATZ. For this objective, a reduced-scale replica was conducted by spiking the same soil with GLY and ATZ (100 ug kg^{-1}). Here, 100 g of the spiked soil were treated with peroxide aqueous solutions containing 10, 20, 40, and 90 mg of H_2O_2 , equivalent to the treatments in the plant pots at 2, 7, 15, and 30 days. As expected, the removal of ATZ and GLY increases with higher oxidant doses (Table 5). For instance, 19.9, 25.9, 50.3, and 67.6% of the initial ATZ was eliminated after adding 10, 20, 40, and 90 mg of H_2O_2 , respectively. For GLY, the removals were 0.1, 14.1, 22.3, and 25.2%. This data also corroborated what was presented above in spiked artificial soils, where H_2O_2 was more efficient at eliminating ATZ than GLY.

Table 5. Atrazine and Glyphosate removal after treatment with different doses of hydrogen peroxide

H ₂ O ₂ Dose	ATZ degradation (%)	GLY degradation (%)
10 mg	19.9	0.1
20 mg	25.9	14.1
40 mg	50.3	22.3
90 mg	67.6	25.2

Effects on biodiversity

The effect of the hydrogen peroxide treatment on soil biodiversity was assessed with nematode mortality (percentage of death nematodes in the sample in relation to the number of total nematode sample and extracted by centrifugal-flotation) and soil respirometry using MicroResp(R). Figure 11 presents the evolution of plant-parasitic and free-living nematodes in the experiments conducted for 7, 15, and 30 days. In addition, control experiments are included, where the same volume of water without the oxidant was added. Interestingly, the mortality of free-living nematodes does not change significantly between the control and the treated soils during the first 15 days. However, a slightly larger variation is observed after 30 days. As for the plant-parasitic nematodes, a noticeable difference in mortality is seen in respect to the control in 15 and 30 days, which suggests that H₂O₂ damages this group of nematodes. Another important observation is the large variation in nematode mortality for all the samples, likely attributed to the heterogeneity of real soils. It is difficult to explain why plant-parasitic nematodes are more damage than free-living nematodes. One option could be that free-living nematodes could be selected, and the selected nematodes genus are adapted to these conditions (mainly bacterivorous), while plant-parasitic nematodes need plants to multiply and once nematodes die by some stress (in this case H₂O₂), they need plants to multiply and the experiment was conducted without plants.

Figure 11. Nematode mortality during the remediation of agricultural soils with hydrogen peroxide

Figure 12 shows the respirometry data in the soil during the remediation with H₂O₂. Consistent with what was observed above, overall basal and substrate induced respiration rates decreased over time, yet the control shows a superior metabolic rate than H₂O₂ treatments. This corroborates the overall negative impact of this oxidant on microbial activity, with the exception of the bacteria that use the n-acetyl glucosamine (NAGA), as a substrate after 30 days .

Figure 12. Respiration rates during the remediation of agricultural soils with hydrogen peroxide.

2.4. Subtask 4. Chemical remediation of soil with gaseous O₃ electrogenerated

The scheme for the remediation of soil with electrochemically produced ozone is illustrated in Figure 13. In summary, ozone is produced in the PEM cell and fed into a tank containing the electrolyte, which is recirculated into the system. The O₃ gaseous phase is then introduced to the mock-up bottom, increasing the contact with soil while moving along to the mock-up top. 120 g of soil contaminated with oxyfluorfen and atrazine in concentrations of 0.1 and 1.5 mg kg⁻¹ was placed inside the mock-up. Ozone was introduced at a flow rate of approximately 0.27 mg min⁻¹ for 120 minutes, feeding 32.4 mg of the oxidant. Similar to the treatment with H₂O₂, the mock-up was divided into three similar sections to evaluate potential differences in the residual pesticide concentrations, as ozone might not be equally distributed along the mock-up. The content of the herbicides in the soil samples was extracted following a QuEChERS extraction method and measured by HPLC-MS.

Figure 13. Installation and mock-up for soil remediation with ozone

Experiments were conducted using spiked soil with oxyfluorfen and atrazine at concentrations of 0.1 and 1.5 mg kg⁻¹, with ozone electrochemically produced at 3 and 4 A. Table 6 presents a comparison of the percentage removal of atrazine and oxyfluorfen at 1.5 mg kg⁻¹ of contamination. Interestingly, higher removals were obtained for both herbicides in the bottom sections, which significantly dropped by more than 50% in the top sections. This suggests that ozone successfully reacts with both pesticides, especially in the bottom where the ozone initially enters and flows through the system, but as degradation occurs, the concentration in the gas phase is reduced, lowering the availability of the oxidant in the upper sections. In terms of current intensity, it seems that slightly higher removals were obtained for both OXY and ATZ with the ozone produced at 4A, likely due to an increased production rate of the oxidant.

Table 6. % of pesticides (1500 µg/kg) eliminated using ozone electrochemically produced at 3 and 4 A.

Intensity	Section	OXY Removal (%)	ATZ Removal (%)
3A	A	20.7	17.5
	B	49.7	41.4
	C	77.9	65.9
4A	A	36.9	12.1
	B	59.5	43.5
	C	80.3	67.6

To understand the influence of the pesticide concentration, further experiments were conducted using spiked soil in concentrations of 0.1 mg kg⁻¹ and treated with ozone generated at 4 A. OXY and ATZ removals are presented in Table 7. In general, the removal of OXY was favoured over ATZ in the three sections, as 86.1 and 66.7% of OXY and ATZ were eliminated, respectively. Of interest here is that OXY was equally removed in the three sections, while ATZ degradation was largely higher at the bottom of the mock-up. Comparing these results with those of the previous section, OXY removals were comparable to the ones obtained in the

mock-up bottom, suggesting that the amount of ozone is sufficient to degrade over 80% of this pesticide at lower concentrations. Surprisingly, ATZ degradation was diminished when the contaminant concentration was reduced to 0.1 mg kg⁻¹, which is more evident in the top section, where null degradation was observed. Since the oxidant is fed from the bottom section, it seems that a considerable amount of ozone was consumed here, diluting the oxidant gas stream that reaches the upper sections. Overall, it is suggested that ozone possesses higher efficiency to chemically degrade oxyfluorfen than atrazine in spiked soils.

Table 7. Pesticide removals (100 µg/kg) using ozone electrochemically produced at 4 A.

Section	OXY Removal (%)	ATZ Removal (%)
A	84.8	0.0
B	88.7	24.7
C	86.1	66.7

For the study of the effect of ozonation on soil biodiversity, soil samples from the orchard ES-HD22 were treated with O₃ gas, similarly to the ones presented with H₂O₂. The variation of GLY concentration, along with a study of the nematode mortality and soil respirometry, was conducted in independent experiments for 2, 7, 15 and 30 days. They were carried out in triplicate. In addition, blank experiments were conducted using the same experimental conditions but without the injection of ozone to draw a baseline of natural decline in microbial activity. Ozone was electrochemically produced on demand with the dual-compartment PEM cell (prototype 2). On average, 0.23 mg min⁻¹ of ozone was generated in the anode by the oxidation of water at a current density of 282 mA cm⁻². The ozone gas was injected into the plant pots using the same 3D-printed pipes used in the treatment of spiked soils. O₃ was fed into the system through the bottom of the pot to increase the exposure area of the soil to the oxidant while flowing upwards. A schematic representation of the process is presented in Figure 14. To increase the soil's pore spaces and enhance ozone diffusion, air was passed through the mock-ups for 1 hour prior to starting the experiment.

Figure 14. Scheme of the ozonation process for removing organic pesticides from agricultural soils.

To determine the O₃ dose compared to the mass of GLY in the soil, O₃ concentration was continuously measured in the inlet gas stream. The evolution of the accumulated O₃ mass over time is presented in Figure 15. One of the most notable aspects of the graph is the steady O₃ production in the 30 days of experiments, demonstrating the durability and continuous operating capacity of the PEM cell design. With this feeding rate, 27.0, 97.8, 213.1, and 618.8 mg were introduced into the system after 2, 7, 15, and 30 days, representing an oxidant to contaminant ratio of 60, 230, 500, and 1500 (wt.), respectively.

Figure 15. Accumulated mass of O₃ that was injected into the mock-ups during the treatment.

As already explained, the concentration of GLY was below the detection limits in this soil, and thus, soil from the same orchard was spiked with ATZ and GLY. Concentrations of 100 ug kg⁻¹ of each pesticide in the soil were aimed for, and the ozone dosage was calculated based on the oxidant to contaminant ratio from the experiments described above. For instance, ozonation (0.5 mg min⁻¹) of 100 g of spiked soil was conducted for 5, 15, 30, and 60 mins, which are equivalent to the ozonation in the plant pots for 2, 7, 15, and 30 days. The reduction in the concentration of GLY and ATZ after different times of ozonation is presented in Table 8. Overall, longer ozonation treatments increased the contaminant removal. For instance, ATZ removals of 14.5, 33.4, 24.4, and 44.4% were achieved after ozonation for 5, 15, 30, and 60 mins. It is worth noting that the O₃ concentration in the outlet gas stream was also measured, where minimal quantities of the oxidant were detected in all the experiments, indicating the successful reactivity of O₃ with the organic matter in the soil. The lower removal after 30 mins compared to the one at 15 mins may be attributed to the difference in gas diffusion. Despite using the same soil, O₃ diffusion pathways are formed upon gas injection, and the presence of any resistance affects their optimum spread, which is more evident in short experiments. As for GLY, removals of 4.5, 6.2, 6.3, and 21.1% were achieved after ozonation for 5, 15, 30, and 60 mins. Interestingly, higher ATZ degradation efficiencies were achieved, which is contrary to what was seen in the ozonation of spiked artificial soils. This highlights the repercussions of using real soils as the matrix where the oxidant can interact differently with the organic matter and determines the need to study the degradation efficiency of chemical oxidation in soils from Mediterranean olive groves.

Table 8. Atrazine and Glyphosate removal after treatment with different ozonation times

Ozonation time	ATZ degradation (%)	GLY degradation (%)
5 min	14.5	4.5
15 min	33.4	6.2
30 min	24.4	6.3
60 min	44.4	21.1

These experiments confirmed the feasibility of producing ozone and hydrogen peroxide with MEA electrochemical cells in mass rates over 0.2 and 10 mg min⁻¹, respectively. Using these oxidants directly in the soil, promising oxyfluorfen and atrazine degradations above 50 % were obtained, depending on the pesticide concentration in the soil. Of interest here is that ozone favoured the OXY degradation while hydrogen peroxide degraded ATZ to a higher degree; however, both oxidants could reduce pesticide concentrations in soil. Future work will involve testing on real (non-spiked) soils to determine the optimal oxidant dosage in co-contaminated soil where more pollutants are likely to be present.

Effects on biodiversity

The impact of O₃ treatment on soil microbial biodiversity was evaluated through nematode mortality (percentage of death nematodes in the sample in relation to the number of total nematode sample and extracted by centrifugal-flotation) and MicroResp(R) soil respirometry analyses. Figure 16 illustrates the temporal variation of plant-parasitic and free-living nematode mortality after 7, 15, and 30 days of treatment. Control tests are also included, in which an air current without the oxidant was passed along the soil in the pots. Of interest here is the slight variation in mortality of both plant-parasitic and free-living nematodes between the control and treated soils. Importantly, this indicates that ozone does not damage these groups of nematodes. A large variation is observed in and between the pots, which is associated with the heterogeneity of the soil and sampling. It is worth noting that *Pratylenchus* (plant-parasitic endoparasite) has emerged as the roots begin to decompose after 30 days of treatment.

Figure 16. Nematode mortality (range 0-1) during the remediation of agricultural soils with ozone

Figure 17 shows the respirometry data in the soil during the remediation with O₃. As expected, the both basal and induced-substrate respiration rates do not decrease significantly over time. Interestingly, minor differences are observed between the control and the treated soil, which corroborates the minor effect of O₃ on microbial activity. These findings are pivotal, as they demonstrate the feasibility and biological safety of treating contaminated agricultural soils with ozone gas.

Figure 17. Respiration rates during the remediation of agricultural soils with ozone.

2.5. Subtask 5. Electrokinetic remediation of soil polluted with copper.

Electrokinetic remediation involves the application of an electric field to the soil via two electrodes: an anode, where water oxidation occurs, and a cathode, where water reduction takes place. As explained above, this process can induce the mobilisation of copper in the soil by different electrochemical-driven mechanisms such as electroosmosis, electromigration, and electrophoresis (Figure 18). Due to the low solubility of copper-based fungicides, the latter mechanisms are more likely to remove Cu from soil through the transport of Cu ions or Cu particle-like aggregations towards the anode or cathode, depending on their charge. For this reason, the electrodes are placed in wells to facilitate the accumulation and extraction of copper.

To prove the copper extraction capacity of some common chelating agents in real contaminated soil, washing batch tests were first carried out with nitric (HNO_3), citric, ethylenediaminetetraacetic (EDTA), and ethylenediamine-N,N'-disuccinic (EDDS) acid. Typically, 10 g of soil was mixed with 20 mL of the washing solutions and agitated (150 rpm) for 24 hours. The mixture was then centrifuged (5000 rpm) for 10 minutes to separate the liquid and solid phases. Copper concentration was measured in both phases to determine the mass of copper removed by the solution (in the liquid phase) and the mass retained in the soil (solid phase). The percentage of copper extracted (Table 9) indicates that nitric and citric acids did not efficiently remove the metal from the real contaminated soil since less than 4% of the copper content was recovered. On the other hand, removals over 30% were obtained with EDTA and EDDS. It has been established that these organic acids form stable metal complexes with Cu ions, increasing their mobility and solubilisation. Therefore, these results indicate the need to use chelating agents that can act as ligands for Cu to enhance its removal, likely due to the strong retention in the soil.

Figure 18. Processes that take place in the soil during electrokinetic remediation.

Table 9. Percentage of copper removal from real soil using different washing solutions.

Washing solution	% Cu extracted
Water	0.06
HNO_3 0.1M	0.62
Citric Acid 0.1M	3.58
EDTA 0.1M	35.81
EDDS 0.1M	30.38

To further demonstrate the strong retention of Cu ions in this soil, washing experiments with the same soil/washing fluid ratio were conducted using spiked soil, which can simulate lower metal adsorption. Cuprocalcium sulfate and copper oxychloride were used since they are the active agents of most of the Cu-based fungicides used by local farmers. The concentration of copper was set at 50 mg kg^{-1} to replicate the contamination levels of the real soil. As expected, the extraction capacity of the chelating agents was noticeably improved for both formulations, except for citric acid (Table 10). Surprisingly, the removal of Cu with nitric acid increased from 0.62% in the real soil to over 33% in the spiked soil. This value is close to the ones presented in the literature for spiked soils, suggesting that nitric acid effectiveness is limited to spiked soils where metal retention is less appreciable. Another important aspect of the table is the lower extraction in the soil contaminated with copper oxychloride, corroborating the influence of Cu-based fungicide

formulations on copper mobility identified in previous research. These data also allow us to confirm the higher extraction capacity of the Cu-ligands EDTA and EDDS.

Table 10. Percentage of copper removal from spiked soil (Cuprocalcium sulfate and Copper oxychloride) using different washing solutions.

Washing solution	% Cu extracted	
	Cuprocalcium Sulfate	Copper Oxychloride
Water	0.26	0.52
HNO₃ 0.1M	39.68	33.76
Citric Acid 0.1M	0.62	3.38
EDTA 0.1M	52.60	48.44
EDDS 0.1M	49.32	40.56

Having defined the extraction capacity of chelating agents, electrokinetic remediation of the real soil was conducted at the lab scale. Acrylic square containers of 17 cm length × 3 cm width × 15 cm height were used as mock-ups with electrode chambers on the sides where graphite bars (11 cm × 1 cm × 1 cm) were placed as the electrodes (Figure 19). The anode and cathode were connected to a DC electric power source (Delta Elektronika ES030–10). The mock-ups were divided into three compartments: the central compartment for soil, and the side compartments for the electrolytes, each containing approximately 300 g of soil and 50 mL of the anolyte and catholyte. During the operation, the current intensity, volume of transported water, pH, and copper concentration in the electrolyte were daily monitored. In addition, the electrolytes were replaced day-to-day with 50 mL of fresh solutions.

Figure 19. Mock-up for the electrokinetic remediation.

Firstly, preliminary EK experiments with water as the electrolyte were conducted in gravel, sand, clay, and real soils for 24 hours to understand copper mobility in different soil matrices. For this purpose, gravel, sand, and clay were artificially contaminated with copper sulphate heptahydrate (1 g l^{-1}). In addition, real soil was tested as received and with the addition of this sulphate to determine the effect of aged contamination (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Preliminary electrokinetic tests.

Quantitative analysis of copper in the anolyte and catholyte by AAS (Table 11) shows significant differences in the mobilised Cu depending on the soil matrix. In the cathodic well, larger Cu mobilisation is observed in clay (66.04 mg), followed by sand (51.22 mg), spiked real soil (42.80 mg), and gravel (36.08 mg). This suggests that Cu mobilisation to the cathode depends on water movement (electroosmosis) since clay is composed of fine particles, which reduce permeability and enhance electroosmosis, while gravel minimises water mobilisation due to its high content of coarse particles. Contrary to electroosmosis, electromigration is promoted in soil with high permeability, explaining the higher mass of copper measured in the anodic well for gravel (27.42 mg). In addition, it seems that the soil from the olive grove hinders the electrochemical-driven movement of Cu ions, particularly in the real soil that was not artificially contaminated, where only 0.01 and 0.06 mg of Cu were measured in the anode and cathode, respectively. This corroborates the presence of strongly retained copper in the real soil, as approximately 15 mg of Cu were estimated to be available. Despite observing Cu mobilisation, this does not represent more than 8% of the total copper added, which is somewhat expected since ultra-pure water was used as the electrolyte.

Table 11. Mobilised Copper after 24h in the preliminary tests.

Mobilised Cu (mg)	Anodic well	Cathodic well
Gravel	27.42	36.08
Sand	21.96	51.22
Clay	14.38	66.04
Real soil + copper (Spiked)	5.73	42.80
Real soil	0.01	0.06

Citric acid 0.5 M was first tested as an alternative anolyte in the EKR to increase the mobilisation of retained copper. It was selected because of its natural occurrence and readily biodegradability, minimising potential negative effects in the treated soil. Like the previous EKR with water, this test was conducted at 1 V cm^{-1} as well as 1.6 V cm^{-1} . Analysis of the intensity evolution (Figure 21) indicates that this electrolyte provides stable electrical parameters for 360 h, which is key to promoting electrochemical-driven processes. A typical intensity drop is observed after 200 hours of operation, especially at 1.6 V cm^{-1} , caused by the migration of ions under the application of direct current.

Figure 21. Variation of current intensity during EKR tests using citric acid.

Unfortunately, the operation of this mock-up was not continued over 360 hours due to the formation of white crusts (Figure 22) resulting from the precipitation of carbonates, diminishing electroosmotic flux. This outcome was rather predictable since the concentration of carbonates in this soil ranged from 0.9 to 79 mg/kg, which can precipitate upon formation of calcium citrate or citrate-calcium complexes.

Figure 22. Picture citric Acid mock-up after 400h of operation at 1 V/cm .

As a result, another test was conducted using EDTA 0.1M as the chelating agent at 1.6 V cm^{-1} . Likewise, the electrical current exhibited the typical behaviour of an EKR: a slight increase at the beginning of the experiment that drops until eventually reaching a plateau. It is worth noting that this chelating agent did not promote the precipitation of carbonates.

Having identified the feasibility of using EDTA in the EK process, a general analysis of the main parameters of the process is explained below. One of the most important parameters to control in the EK remediation of agricultural soils is the pH, since the application of sufficient electrical current splits water, creating highly acidic or basic conditions that may affect soil quality. Soil pH was daily measured in the centre of the mock-up (Figure 23), where little variation was identified compared to the initial pH for 360 hours of operation. This could indicate a buffering capacity of the soil since pHs of 12 and 2 were determined from the beginning of the EKR in the catholyte and anolyte, respectively.

Figure 23. Variation of pH in the soil (a) and wells (b) during the EKR-test with 0.1M EDTA

Water mobilisation to the cathode is expected in the EKR because of the interaction of the applied electric fields (electroosmosis). Therefore, the water volume that left the anode and reached the cathode was estimated day-to-day to understand the electroosmotic flux (Figure 24). Approximately -0.69 and 0.22 mL h^{-1} were moved from the anode well and towards the cathode well, respectively, indicating that more than 50% of the added water was absorbed in the particle soils, likely due to low soil moisture. An electroosmotic flux of 0.32 cm d^{-1} was calculated considering the volume electrochemically transported to the cathode.

Figure 24. Volume mobilised to both wells during the experiment.

Contrary to what was observed for the Cu mobilisation to the electrode wells in the EKR with water, there is a difference of more than 20-fold in the metal collection in the anode compared to the cathode (Table 12). This indicates that the mobilisation is driven by the complexation of EDTA with Cu ions, which have a negative charge and are transported to the positive electrode (anode) by electromigration/electrophoresis. Another important aspect of the graph is the linear relationship between accumulated mobilised Cu and time, showing that Cu is continuously removed in both electrode wells during the operation of the EKR.

Table 12. Copper (mg) mobilised to the wells during the electrokinetic remediation.

Time (hours)	Anode	Cathode
	Cu mobilised (mg)	Cu mobilised (mg)
4	0.008	0.014
24	0.074	0.023
48	0.308	0.037
120	0.734	0.050
144	1.713	0.075
192	2.176	0.087
216	2.450	0.099
288	2.642	0.106
312	2.864	0.116
336	3.092	0.125
360	3.343	0.133

Several other experiments were conducted with a combination of chelating agents in the catholyte and anolyte at electric fields of 1 and 1.6 V cm⁻¹ for 20 days to understand the best conditions to increase Cu extraction, as summarised in Table 13. Consistent with what was presented above, low extraction capacity (below 5%) is observed for the systems with citric and nitric acids as the catholytes, while the addition of EDTA or EDDS improved the extraction to over 10%. Interestingly, extraction was enhanced by the addition of EDTA to the catholyte rather than to the anolyte. For example, 28.3% of copper was extracted with EDTA 0.1 M as the catholyte and citric acid 0.05M as the anolyte, which dropped to 11.05% by using the electrolytes in the opposite well. This is likely attributed to the basic pH in the catholyte, inducing the deprotonation of EDTA and further mobilisation to the anode due to the negative charge (-4), which enhances complexation with Cu ions. The addition of EDTA to both electrolytes induces minor effects on mobilisation. Another important aspect of the table is that higher current intensities were achieved in experiments with EDTA and EDDS, suggesting that these chelating agents may improve soil conductivity. Finally, analysis of copper extraction based on the copper concentration calculated with the alternative method increases the values over 50%, which are comparable to the ones obtained in the literature for spiked soils, confirming that there is a considerable portion of strongly retained copper.

Table 13. Summary of the primary results of the EKR tests with the soil from the olive orchards.

Test	Anolyte	Catholyte	Electric Field (V/cm)	Average intensity (A)	Q (Ah)	% extracted of copper	% extracted of copper *
1	Water	Citric Acid 0.1M	1	0.014	5.25	2.50	
2	Water	Citric Acid 0.5M	1	0.015	5.73	1.38	
3	Water	Nitric Acid 0.1M	1	0.021	7.62	1.10	
4	Water	Nitric Acid 0.5M	1	0.021	5.90	3.30	
5	Water	Citric Acid 0.1M	1.6	0.020	7.36	0.82	
6	Water	Citric Acid 0.5M	1.6	0.024	9.14	3.91	
7	Water	Nitric Acid 0.1M	1.6	0.022	7.93	1.49	
8	Water	Nitric Acid 0.5M	1.6	0.023	6.32	4.61	

9	EDTA 0.1M	Citric Acid 0.05M	1.6	0.031	9.48	11.05	24.1
10	Citric Acid 0.05M	EDTA 0.1M	1.6	0.056	7.70	28.3	58.5
11	EDTA 0.1M	EDTA 0.1M	1.6	0.057	19.89	24.87	39.3
12	EDTA 0.1M	EDTA 0.1M	1.6	0.056	18.06	21.37	33.7
13	EDTA 0.1M	EDTA 0.1M	1.6	0.052	15.99	32.58	51.4
14	Water / 0.1 M EDTA (central point) / Water		1.6	0.02	8.16	5.59	8.8
15	Water / 0.1 M EDTA (central point) Water		1.6	0.03	9.40	16.70	26.4
16	Citric Acid 0.05M	EDDS 0.01M	1.6	0.02	5.30	21.35	27.3
17	Citric Acid 0.05M	EDDS 0.01M	1.6	0.02	4.12	22.92	29.3
18	Citric Acid 0.05M	EDDS 0.01M	1.6	0.03	7.35	17.15	22.7

* Percentage of removal estimated based on copper concentration measured with the non-reflux method

Overall, the relevance of EKR for Cu removal is clearly supported by our findings despite the strong retention of the metal on the soil particles. High retention also affected Cu mobility, requiring the use of chelating agents that can form stable complexes with the metal cations. However, only EDTA and EDDS were proven to enhance mobility to a considerable rate compared to the EKR with water, particularly towards the anode due to the negative charge of these complexes. It seemed that intensity played an important role in this improvement, as EDTA and EDDS increased current intensity, which directly affects electrochemical-driven processes. Surprisingly, the electro-osmotic flux was stable for all the treatments, obtaining values around 0.2-0.4 cm d⁻¹.

Following the recommendations of the reviewers, a study of the potential side effects on soil fertility and biodiversity with electrokinetic remediation was conducted, which will shed light on determining the optimal conditions for increasing pollutant removal with minimal effects on soil quality. Here, electrokinetic-induced mobility of copper (Cu) in contaminated soils from the orchard ES-HD22 were analysed. Several soil samples were collected in rectangular plant pots (17 x 60 x 19.5 cm³) from different areas of the orchard, which is estimated to have 72.57 mg Cu kg⁻¹. The soil samples were treated as received without homogenisation to

replicate real-world environments. EDDS (0.05 M) was added as a chelating agent to enhance ion mobility since strong Cu retention was previously reported in this soil, which can negatively affect its removal. EDDS was selected due to their low toxicity and biocompatibility. In this experiment, electrode wells were not excavated, but rather the electrodes were directly placed into the soil to reduce the interference of external factors and include accurate information about the impact of the treatment on soil biodiversity. For this reason, the EDTA aqueous solutions were introduced into the system by dispersing 100 ml on top of the soil every day with a syringe. To understand the effect of the remediation over time, the EKR was conducted in triplicate for 2, 7, 15, and 30 days in independent experiments. In addition, blank tests were simultaneously tested without the application of electric fields and the chelating agent (only water was applied). The EKR operated in potentiostatic mode where the electric field was fixed at 1.6 V cm^{-1} . A power supply was used to distribute the electric field in parallel, as seen in Figure 25.

Figure 25. Scheme of the electrokinetic remediation of agricultural soil from the orchard ES-HD22.

The current intensity at the power supply was continuously monitored over the operation of the EKR, as presented in Figure 26. A common electrical behaviour is observed, where the maximum current intensities of approximately 480 mA are reached during the first 7 days due to the even distribution of ions across the treatment area. Then, it gradually dropped to 150 mA after 30 days of continuous operation due to the redistribution of the ions: anion to the anode and cation to the cathode. This may induce a higher electrical resistance in the medium, decreasing the flow of electric current.

Figure 26. Time evolution of the current intensity during the EKR of agricultural soil from the orchard ES-HD22.

Since the operation of the EKR can generate an acidic front (anode) and a basic front (cathode), the pH of the soil close to the anode, centre, and cathode was continuously followed (Figure 27). Surprisingly, the pH of soil near the cathode increased rapidly from 7.9 (initial) to 12.0 in only 3 days due to the reduction of water and remained steady afterwards. On the other hand, the pH at the anode gradually reduced from 7.9 to 4.5 in 30 days because of the oxidation of water. This may indicate that the soil acted as a buffer for the protons generated at the anode, likely attributed to the presence of carbonates in the soil. The pH in the centre between the electrodes did not change significantly, as values close to 8.0 were recorded, similar to the pH before the EK treatment. As the pHs greatly varied across the treatment area, we defined the need to separately analyse soil biodiversity in samples taken from the anode, cathode, and centre. This will expand the knowledge of how different pHs affect soil microbial activity in EKR.

Figure 27. Evolution of pH over time at the anode, cathode, and centre during the EKR.

To control the volume of water retained in the soil after adding aqueous EDTA solutions, soil moisture was monitored at both the anodic and cathodic ends (Figure 28). Here, we expected to find important differences in the anode and cathode since water mobilisation towards the cathode occurs under the application of electric fields via electro-osmosis. Due to the addition of daily doses of 100 ml of the chelating agent, the soil moisture increased over the first days of the treatment until reaching a maximum value close to 40%. This might indicate that the water saturation point was attained when the soil pores are full of water, and excess water just drained from the drainage holes located at the bottom of the mock-ups. This was corroborated at the end of the experiment when the mock-up was disassembled, and water was found on the bottom. After reaching the saturation point, the variation in the moisture content may be related to the evaporation of water. It is possible that water naturally evaporated since the mock-ups were open to the environment. Of interest here is that soil moisture in the soil near the cathode was slightly higher only during the first 7 days, likely attributed to electro-osmotic flow from the anode to the cathode. Then, a defined trend in soil moisture was not observed, which could be a result of operating at the water saturation point; thus, the mobilised water to the cathodic end might have drained from the bottom of the mock-up.

Figure 28. Evolution of soil moisture over time at the anode and the cathode during the EKR.

Due to the absence of electrolyte wells to remove the flushing fluids containing the mobilised copper, we focused on analysing Cu mobility in the soil by measuring Cu concentration within the treated area. The average profile concentrations in the mock-ups are represented in a 2-D heatmap before and after the EKR for 2, 7, 15, and 30 days (Figure 29). As expected, the initial dry basis concentration (concentration per dry soil) in the mock-ups varies significantly, ranging from 615.0 mg kg⁻¹ to 60.7 mg kg⁻¹, which is expected in contaminated soils without prior homogenisation. Notably, higher concentrations are observed in the surface horizon, which is somewhat expected since Cu-based fungicides are applied on top of the soil, and we directly tested the EKR in mock-ups that were collected from the olive orchard without pretreatments. Interestingly, the average Cu concentration profiles after the remediation show important mobilisation towards the anode, where higher concentrations were found. This is explained by the formation of Cu-EDDS complexes, which are negatively charged and might mobilise to the anode by electromigration or electrophoresis.

d)

Figure 29. Cu concentration (mg kg^{-1}) profile in the mock-ups before and after the EK remediation for a) 2 days, b) 7 days, c) 15 days, and d) 30 days.

In addition, a more extensive post-treatment chemical characterisation of the EKR was conducted in the test operated for 15 days or more, as potential Cu-precipitates were observed on top of the mock-ups. In these cases, several sampling points were taken, including a thin layer of approximately 2 cm from the top. Figure 30b shows the results obtained in the test operated for 15 days. It indicates the accumulation of copper on the surface layer with concentrations of up to 816.4 mg kg^{-1} , demonstrating the precipitation of Cu salts (potentially copper carbonate hydroxide) due to the presence of carbonates and basic pHs at the basic front. These salts were not observed in the blank tests (without EDDS addition). Furthermore, these graphs corroborate the migration of Cu ions to the anode, where higher concentrations were detected, confirming that EKR can mobilise Cu ions in real agricultural soils toward the electrodes, thereby decontaminating areas farther from the anode

a)

b)

Cathode			Anode			
170.9	816.4					170.9
	200.5	183.0	189.6	287.4	252.0	
	97.5	167.9	166.9	229.1	200.7	
170.9						

Figure 30. a) Photograph of potential Cu-salt precipitates. b) Detailed Cu concentration (mg kg^{-1}) profile in the mock-ups after the EK remediation for 15 days.

Effects on biodiversity

To analyse the effect of the EKR on soil biodiversity, the mortality of nematodes (percentage of death nematodes in the sample in relation to the number of total nematode sample and extracted by centrifugal-flotation) and soil respirometry analyses by using Microresp(R) were carried out. Figure 31 illustrate the temporal variation of plant-parasitic and free-living nematode mortality after 7, 15, and 30 days of treatment. Overall, it seems that longer EKR times increase mortality. In the case of the free-living nematodes, there is no variation in the control, but mortality dramatically jumps to the highest after 30 days, particularly near the cathode. This is somewhat expected since the reduction of water can generate hydroxyl ions, increasing the soil pH and damaging the nematodes. As for the plant-parasitic nematodes, lower mortalities were identified at the centre. However, this is a treatment with a long period of time changing the soil conditions in the pot depending of the anode, cathode or center just as pH or other toxic elements are distributed, so additionally to mortality, the nematode migration could be an important point to evaluate the technique. Figure 32 presents the total abundance of nematodes in 100 cm^3 of soil in each region of the pot. This data showed higher nematode abundance in the center and similar levels of nematodes in anode and cathode. A reduction of total nematode abundance is detected in general after 30 days. As in other experiments, a selection and

multiplication or migration of some specific nematode genera is detected in the more extreme areas of the pot, probably influenced by change in soil microbiome (mainly free-living nematodes) or changes in pH levels. A high variability in the data is detected as are in biological soil experiments.

Figure 31. Nematode mortality (expressed from 0-1) during the electrokinetic remediation of agricultural soils

Figure 32. Nematode abundance (100 cm³ of soil) during the electrokinetic remediation of agricultural soils

Figure 33 presents soil respirometry data after the EKR and the control without applied electric current. Samples near the anode and cathode, as well as from the centre of the plot, were measured. Overall, the both soil basal and substrate-induced microbial respiration decreases over time for all the samples, which is somewhat expected due to substrate consumption. However, what is interesting is that the electric current and the chelating agent EDDS did not affect the soil respiration rates. In fact, there are some points where the control presents the lowest microbial respiration. This is contrary to what was observed in the nematode mortality and indicates that the applied electric current and its associated electrokinetic process do not considerably affect soil microbial activity.

Figure 33. Soil respiration rates during the electrokinetic remediation of agricultural soils

Conclusion

- Despite the interest in electrokinetic remediation and chemical oxidation to treat pollutants in soils, previous research has been limited to applications in spiked soils or industrial soils. The challenge of agricultural soil remediation lies in the potential negative effects on microbial activity, which can undermine nutrient cycling, soil structure, and soil fertility. In addition, co-contamination of several other pollutants in real soils can dramatically reduce the efficiency of the remediation. Hence, it is pivotal to conduct detailed studies of any remediation approach before scaling it to field applications, ensuring efficacy, optimising operating windows, and mitigating microbial activity impact.
- **Chemical oxidation** using electrochemically generated ozone gas and hydrogen peroxide aqueous solutions achieved significant removals of common pesticides in soils. For instance, hydrogen peroxide reached removals over 90% and 67% of atrazine in spiked and agricultural soil from the orchard ES-HD22, respectively. This difference corroborates that parameters often not considered in artificial soils, such as co-contamination and soil permeability, play a crucial role in remediation efficiency. Furthermore, efficiency dropped to 25% with glyphosate in agricultural soil, indicating that the hydrogen peroxide oxidation rate may differ between organic pollutants. Similarly, ozone decreased the concentration of atrazine by 68% and 45% in spiked and the same agricultural soil. As for glyphosate degradation in agricultural soil, a comparable 44% removal was achieved, indicating that ozonation is not selective to organic contaminants and can oxidise a wide range of pollutants. In both oxidation treatments, we found higher contaminant removals in areas close to the oxidant addition point, showing oxidant diffusion dependency on the treatment. A comprehensive assessment of nematode mortality and respiration rates showed a negative effect of hydrogen peroxide, but a minimal effect of ozone gas. It is important to note that daily dosing of

hydrogen peroxide in water may have contributed to this outcome, whereas ozone likely had a minor impact because it was delivered as a gas stream. Overall, these findings highlight the feasibility of degrading organic pollutants with both oxidants; however, ozonation is preferred for maintaining soil microbial activity after treatment. We also demonstrated that the proposed electrochemical reactor designs allowed continuous and prolonged operation for the generation of hydrogen peroxide and ozone gas.

- As for the **electrokinetic remediation** of olive orchard soils contaminated with Cu-based fungicides, strong Cu retention within the soil matrix was determined, increasing the complexity to mobilise this heavy metal and reduce its concentration in soil. Hence, chelating agents were required to enhance removal efficiency, with ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and ethylenediamine-N, N'-disuccinic acid (EDDS) achieving the highest removals. For instance, over 32% and 23% of copper was removed from real soils via electromigration/electrophoresis after 360 hours of remediation using 0.1 M EDTA and 0.1 M EDDS, respectively. EKR at the bench scale with EDDS as the chelating agent demonstrated Cu mobilisation toward the anode, decreasing its concentration in the soil farther from this electrode. In addition, analysis of nematode mortality and respiration rates indicates a low to moderate impact on microbial activity that depends on distance from the electrodes: a higher impact near the electrodes. However, optimising the electrode position can reduce this effect and enhance copper mobilisation. Therefore, these results are promising to demonstrate the feasibility of efficiently removing Cu from olive orchard soils with minimal adverse consequences for soil fertility.
- The effect of the treatment on the olive grove microbial activity and nematode community showed some effect patterns depending on the technique applied. However, the high biological variability among pots and the presence of specific genera that could be selected and multiplied difficult a clear biological pattern effect. In addition, a series of tests is planned in fields to preliminarily evaluate the effect of the treatment strategy on the olive grove microbiome (WP4).

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